

VARIOUS APPROACHES TO EFL LESSON DESIGN AT UNIVERSITY LEVEL

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“The issue I wish to examine is the decision making of experienced teachers- those myriad points in our daily lives as professionals when we must make an on-line judgment as to what is best for our students, whether to stay with the lesson plan, safely on firm ground, or to head out into the uncharted waters of spontaneous discourse” (Bailey K. 1996, p. 15)

Rezumat: *Predarea unei limbi străine este o muncă grea și asiduă. Înainte de a intra la oră un profesor de limbă străină trebuie să ia în considerare numeroase aspecte ce țin de predarea unei limbi străine, inclusiv de planificare. Pregătirea pentru lecție și planificarea lecției, aspecte esențiale ale procesului de predare a limbilor străine, sunt destul de greu de a învăța, ele îmbunătățindu-se odată cu experiența obținută. Mai mult decât atât, ele nu sunt aspecte izolate de predare, ci sunt o parte importantă a unui proces ciclic global care implică pedagogia, curriculumul, învățarea și evaluarea. Prin urmare, o lecție bună poate fi asigurată numai printr-o procedură bine gândită. Prezentul articol se axează pe aspectul proiectării unei lecții de limba engleză ca limbă străină (EFL) la nivel universitar. Autorii s-au întrebat dacă ar trebui să existe o abordare diferită a planificării EFL în universități față de modelul utilizat în școli și licee. Vom oferi date din propria noastră experiență, precum și date ce reies din înțelegerea acestei probleme de către colegii noștri universitari.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *lecție EFL — engleza ca limbă străină, planificare la nivel universitar, structura lecției, etapele lecției, evocare, realizarea sensului, reflectivă.*

During the last decades English has become one of the most sought-after languages, predominantly by foreign speakers. As a result, the demand for effectual, well-organised English

teaching has increased considerably. The present article touches upon the problem of designing English as a foreign language (EFL) lesson at university level. It examines different types of effective planning. The choice of this topic is motivated both by its significance for up-to-date planning strategies and its usefulness for language teachers, as unlike many other practices in teaching EFL, lesson planning is still an issue to be discussed. The authors have often reflected on whether there should be a different approach to EFL planning in universities compared to the model imposed by the Ministry of Education on primary/ secondary schools and lyceums. While researching the topic we barely found resources dealing with this aspect, subsequently we will carry out the analysis based on the university teachers' professional experience. There are many documents regulating the structure, objectives, competences and the contents of a foreign language lesson in schools, but not in universities. The study of effective lesson planning will definitely lead to better results.

Every teacher needs a basic lesson plan to provide regularity and structure teaching. In the process of planning lessons, teachers can use new tools and quickly adapt to changes in both school course requirements and technology.

According to DeCecco (1974) the process of planning implies the idea that the teacher decides what and how the students should learn. (DeCecco J. 1974, p. 232). A lesson plan is a comprehensive exemplification of what an instructor intends to teach on a certain day. Adriana Vezental (2008) claims that "the function of the lesson plan (or project of didactic technology) is to plan and organize each individual unit of the language course by suggesting concrete activities, techniques, and interaction types for the amount of time taken into consideration; there activities are meant to help the students to achieve certain immediate aims". (Vezental A. 2008, p. 288).

Though the term *lesson plan* seems familiar to all teachers there are numerous explicit definitions provided by various resources. Derrick Meador defines it as "a detailed description of the individual lessons that a teacher plans to teach on a given day. A lesson plan is developed by a teacher to guide instruction throughout the day. It is a method of planning and preparation. (Meador D. on-line) Collin's Dictionary online describes it as "a plan, used by teachers in a school, detailing the structure and format of lessons" (on-line). Bossing (2008) affirms that a "lesson plan is the title given to a statement of the achievements to be realized and the specific meaning by which these are to be attained as the result of the activities engaged during the period." (apud, Singh Y. 2008, p. 28). Cater V. Good (2008) thinks that "a lesson plan is a teaching outline of the important points of a lesson arranged in order in which they are to be presented; it may include objectives, points to be made, questions to be asked, references to materials, assignments, etc." (apud, Singh Y. 2008, p. 212) Lester B. Sands (2008) claims that "a lesson plan is actually a plan of action. It therefore includes the working philosophy of the teacher, her knowledge of philosophy, her information and understanding of her pupils, her comprehension of the objectives of education, her knowledge of the material to be taught, her ability to utilize effective methods) (apud, Singh Y. 2008, p. 212).

Thus a lesson plan is a detailed set of guiding principles of what a teacher plans to do on a particular day. It is an indispensable resource and a 'historical' document that reflects a teacher's training philosophy, students' needs, accessible materials, and definitely the aims and outcomes teachers set for their students.

Considering the above-mentioned we could suggest several features that are directly related to effective lesson planning. Firstly, teachers should write them on a daily basis and plans must be flexible. Secondly, any lesson plan can be considered a draft of various subjects, approaches, strategies, methods, techniques, activities and teaching aids. Moreover it can be regarded as an outline of actions and explicit objectives of lesson planning. Finally, it can be seen as a policy for both the teacher and the student in the process of adopting suitable teaching strategies, methods and techniques.

In order to succeed teachers must be organized and develop lesson plans in a systematic manner. It is common knowledge that there are numerous approaches to lesson planning, for instance:

- The *Project Approach* can be defined as learning in which the students create something beneficial to themselves and the rest of the class. It could be done both individually and in groups. The students get used to applying the scientific method, i.e. how to carry out experiments,

collect and examine the obtained data, analyze the results and present the results (PowerPoint presentation, video journal, written report, etc.) This approach highlights communication, novelty, inventiveness, critical thinking skills, teamwork, and partnership.

- The *Herbartian Approach* comprises the following five steps: Introduction or Motivation, Presentation, Comparison and Association, Generalization, Application and Recapitulation. This is perhaps the approach used in schools in the Republic of Moldova. Other researchers consider calling these five parts: Preparation, Presentation, Practice, Evaluation, and Expansion. A language lesson may contain all of the above-mentioned stages or teachers can extend them for several lessons, depending on the type of the lesson, the topic and the intended activities. According to Adrian Doff (2002) a single lesson will not include all the stages; the stages are in no fixed order; the stages overlap. For example, reading a text might be part of the presentation, or it might be a separate activity. (Doff A. 2002, p.97)

Methodologists also consider three other basic approaches to lesson planning that have both advantages and disadvantages: the linear model, the kaleidoscopic model, and the mixed model.

- The *linear model* suggests a procedure during which the teacher first considers the objectives of the lesson, and then chooses relevant techniques to design lesson activities, as well as testing strategies. Its strong points are transparency, easy implementation, more or less predictable results, effective time and resource management, classroom order, controlled teaching, and knowledge of objectives that helps them to get ready for assessments. The weak points are: inflexible strict teacher-focused instruction, focus on teaching – not on learning, thus inhibiting unplanned activities.
- The *kaleidoscopic model* is based on appealing, thought-provoking activities that are/can be selected by both teachers and students. Being learner-centred, it encourages learners to participate in the educational process according to their personal preferences and needs. Within this model teachers have got certain pre-planned objectives. They announce the topic asking the students to find materials- texts, articles, activities, etc. to exemplify it. Its strong points are: encouraging spontaneity, creativeness, reassuring contradictory and critical thinking skills, justifying diversity, i. e. all students are involved (according to their capacity and needs), leading to unanticipated results and conclusions. The weak points involve difficult classroom management, chaotic aimless activities, vague assessing practices, low quality materials (brought by students), etc.
- The *mixed model* combines both approaches giving teachers the possibility to plan the lesson according to the linear model with an organized logical structure, but permitting the novelty, flexibility and improvisation of classroom activities. This model suggests that learning can be the result of a process of discovery conducted by the teacher.

Special attention should be paid to *the objective-centred character of Bloom's approach* that is explained by its characteristic quality to cover cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning outcomes. This time-consuming model combines educational objectives, learning experiences and change in behaviour and suggests three consecutive stages of its implementation, that is formulation of educational objectives; providing the learning experience appropriate to objectives; and evaluation/change in behaviour. The authors have got the practical skill and expertise in planning an EFL lesson applying Bloom's taxonomy revised version. Each stage of the lesson should be ascribed to one of the six Bloom's levels. The first stage that shows if students can remember the previously acquired information by recalling data terms, facts, basic concepts and answers is called *remembering* (defined as knowledge in the previous variant). Teachers should use such verbs as: *define; duplicate; list; memorize; recall; repeat; reproduce; state; match* and such questions as *How would you describe/ define /explain/show...?, When did ... happen?, Why did...?, Which one...?, Can you list ...?, What is...?, etc.* The second stage called *understanding* (defined as comprehension in the previous variant) shows if students can explain ideas, facts or concepts by organizing, comparing, translating or stating the main idea. Teachers should use such verbs as *classify; describe; discuss; explain; identify; locate; recognize; report; select; translate; paraphrase* and such questions as *Which statement supports the idea...?, What is the main idea?, Which is the best variant? How would you summarize?,*

How would you rephrase the meaning of...?, etc. The third stage is called *applying* (defined as application in the previous variant) shows if students can use the information in a new way. Teachers should use such verbs as: *choose; demonstrate; dramatize; employ; illustrate; interpret; operate; schedule; sketch; solve; use; write* and such questions as *How would you use...?, How will you organize... in order to show...?, What approach would you use to demonstrate...?, What would result if...? What facts would you select to show...?* The fourth stage that shows if students can distinguish between different parts of facts by identifying motives and causes, if they are able to make inferences and find evidence to support the generalization is called *analysing* (defined as *analysis* in the previous version). Teachers should use such verbs as *appraise; compare; contrast; criticize; differentiate; discriminate; distinguish; examine; test; experiment; question; simplify*, and such questions as *How is... related to...?, Why do you think...?, What evidence can you find to prove...?, What motive is there...?, What ideas justify...?, What is the relationship between...?*, etc. The fifth stage called *evaluating* demonstrates if students can justify a stand or decision, defend opinions by making judgments and confirm ideas, or quality of a text based on a set of criteria. It should be noted that the order of levels five and six in the previous version and a new one has been changed, i.e. previous *synthesis* has been substituted by *evaluating*, and *evaluation* by *creating*. At this level teachers should use such verbs as *appraise; argue; defend; judge; select; support; value; evaluate; recommend; determine; criticize; conclude; agree; assess* and such questions as *How would you prioritize...?, Would it be better if...?, How would you rate...?, What judgment would you make about...?, Why was it better that...?, What data was used to make the conclusion...?*, etc. The sixth stage called *creating* shows if students can create a new product or point of view compiling the acquired information together in a different way, or by suggesting alternative solutions. Teachers should use such verbs as *assemble; construct; create; design; develop; formulate; write*, and such questions as *Can you propose an alternative to...?, How would you estimate the results for...?, What facts can you compile to show...?, How would you test...?, What changes would you make to solve...?, Can you invent?*, etc.

It should be mentioned that the updated variant of Bloom's taxonomy has been created to reflect relevance to the 21st century work. Nouns have been replaced by verbs that imply more action.

Primarily, language teachers must be aware of four central issues before entering a class to teach a lesson: "the aim of the lesson; what new language the lesson contains; the main stages of the lesson (i.e. how it divides into different activities) and what to do at each stage." (Doff A. 2002, p. 93).

Moreover, experts consider that lesson plans should reflect the individual needs, strengths, and interests of the teacher and the learners. Developing an effective lesson takes time, endeavour, conscientiousness, and an understanding of the learners' goals and abilities. While planning a lesson teachers should keep in mind that "modern education aims at formation rather than at information, at the process rather than at the product. <...> The means to achieve the aims are viewed as more important than the ends: instead of merely accumulating knowledge and information, learners must be taught to learn- taught to locate new information and use it for real-world purposes". (Vizental A. 2008, p. 290). In other words teachers should teach their students how to teach themselves.

During the planning process a teacher must pay attention to several issues, among which are the students' diverse learning styles, changing his/her teaching style, using different didactic materials, monitoring the students carefully, modifying the instruction as needed, etc. Each lesson plan will depend on the type of the lesson that has constant elements, changing components and common features. Specialists distinguish the following lesson types: Lessons of communication of new knowledge; Combined/mixed lessons; Lessons of fixation of knowledge and of developing skills and abilities/ lessons of reinforcement; Lessons of systematization and revision of knowledge/ Revision Lesson; and Lessons of verification and control of knowledge/ Testing. Accordingly, the lesson plans used by teachers may be presented in many different kinds of formats and styles.

Lesson Structure A foreign language lesson includes a number of activities that combine diverse types of language input and output. However, there are different views on the number of

lesson stages. For instance Jeremy Harmer (1995) affirms that a lesson plan has five major components: “description of the class (portrayal of the students; a statement of time; frequency and duration of the class; comments about physical conditions and/or restrictions), recent work (details about the work students have already done), objectives (aims the teacher has for the students, referring to activities, skills, language type, etc.), contents (it has five headings: context, activity and class organisation; aids; language; possible problems) and additional possibilities.” (Harmer J. 1995, pp. 268-270)

In the Republic of Moldova there are clear-cut instructions (developed by experts under the supervision of the Ministry of Education). There was a period of time when they claimed the lesson should have four stages: Evocation (Motivation), Realization of meaning (Information), Reflection (Practice), and Extension (Application). Only three stages have been left: Evocation, Realization of meaning and Reflection that guarantee the integrity and consistency of the lesson. According to *Ghid de Implementare a Curriculumului Modernizat Pentru Treapta Liceala – Limbi Straine II* (2010, p. 32) “Proiectarea demersului didactic în cheia gândirii critice, <...> nu se limitează la alegerea de tehnici adecvate pentru disciplina și unitatea de învățare respectivă. Etapele cadrului *evocare-realizare a sensului-reflecție* dau integritate și coerență demersului didactic.”

The first stage – *Evocation* (Motivation) is the beginning of the lesson. Its aim is to get all the students interested and involved in the lesson. It also connects the information from the previous lesson with students’ abilities and knowledge. This stage includes the following issues: captivating students’ attention; checking homework; connecting the old and new material; motivating students for the new material. Teachers can do such activities as: discussing personal experiences; talking over a theme/ idea/argument; describing pictures, drawings, posters; brainstorming; mind mapping; listening to a story/ interview/poem; free writing without a topic; clustering; Venn Diagrams; associations, etc.

The second stage is called *Realization of meaning* (Information). Students are familiarized with the new topic (new grammar/vocabulary/text, etc.). During it students make notes, ask questions, and clarify things they have not understood. It is the teacher’s responsibility to explain the new material in a captivating, interesting, comprehensible manner, be it done inductively or deductively. The following activities could be suggested: analyses of diagrams/ tables /charts; Cube; Gigsaw (mosaic); deductive analyses; note taking; Know – don’t know; silent reading (for certain information); controlled exercises; controlled drills (ALM); grammar/ translation (GTM); discussing cultural issues and taking notes; dictations, etc.

The third stage *Reflection* (Practice) gives the students the possibility to practice the information they have learnt in a structured manner. Consequently the students get the chance to consolidate the new material. It is preferable to put accent on critical thinking activities. This stage includes: consolidation; practice; evaluation; and homework (tasks for all 4 skills). Teachers can do the following activities: practical, meaningful exercises; formulating questions for others to answer; exercises requiring critical thinking skills (comparing; contrasting; judging; generalizing; prioritizing, etc.) writing/ revising/ editing paragraphs; multiple choice exercises; matching exercises; pair or/and group work discussions; project planning; case studies; round table discussions; debates; interviews; making diagrams, tables, charts; completing and practicing educational drama activities (language games, role play, skits, reader’s theatre, etc.)

There is one more stage called *Extension* (Application) that comprises activities to be realized after the lesson. They contain out-of-class observation assignments, in which the teachers ask the students to find illustrations for something they have recently learnt, or to apply a newly acquired strategy and then report in class about the results. These activities are based on creativity and critical thinking skills that should be linked to students’ personal lives. In fact it is application of the new material to a new experience that corresponds to Bloom’s level *six-creating*. Teachers can suggest such activities as: writing letters; designing posters, displays, leaflets; writing and sharing poetry, songs, reports, stories, etc.; giving speeches; participating in debates; organizing field-trips; conducting and reporting on interviews and/or surveys; participating in scenarios writing/ skits/ plays, etc.

Still, a teacher should not solely be preoccupied with the careful designing of a lesson plan, as even the most thorough preparation should allow certain flexibility. That is, while delivering a

lesson we should to some extent rely on our experience, constantly keeping in mind that the principal elements of a plan should be primarily considered as explicit guidelines and not as a strict model to follow.

In conclusion we would like again to highlight the requirements for a modern lesson at university level:

- Clearly-cut didactic goals;
- Setting optimal lesson contents according to the Curriculum, lesson objectives and students' level;
- Foreseeing students' level of new data assimilation, of language skills' formation at different stages of the lesson;
- Choice of optimal teaching strategies, approaches, methods, techniques; assessing their influence on the students during each stage of the lesson;
- Ensuring choices that would guarantee students' cognitive activity; combining various forms of group/ pair/ individual work;
- The lesson must set a problem, develop a variety of skills and enhance teacher-student/ student-student collaboration;
- The teacher organizes problem-solving, thought-provoking activities thus stimulating students' participation in class;
- The teacher creates optimal opportunities for students' learning progress.

We consider that, on the one hand, school teachers are in more favourable conditions as they have got exact instructions concerning lesson planning (*Ghid de Implementare*). On the other hand, though University teachers lack clear standards (developed at/by the University) they benefit from more freedom in terms of giving preference to certain approaches to lesson planning that better work in class. We are convinced that there is no perfect model that would correspond to all standards and requirements, so it is teachers' responsibility to make the optimal choice that will be beneficial for their students.

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